

TRADITIONS OF FORMING THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN PEDAGOGY

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the requirements of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, current tasks and the high results achieved under the reforms were mentioned. In pedagogy, young people are spiritual and moral pedagogical features of education formation, including family and education we explained about the role of the system in our thoughts and comments. The role of all of us in the development of young people to become spiritually mature and perfect people is incomparable. I believe that the contribution of pedagogues is great in providing education and training to young people and showing them the right way. Many opportunities have been created for our youth in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The role of education and training in shaping the outlook of our youth is incomparable.

Introduction

To date, the reforms implemented in all sectors in our country, to change people's outlook, mature and meet the requirements of the times life itself requires the training of specialist personnel. In our republic it is important to strengthen the education system and harmonize it with the requirements of the times attention is given. Training, education and upbringing of specialist personnel it is important that the system is closely related to the demands of reforms earns. At the same time, such changes are taking place on a global scale these changes affect the whole nation, nation, nation and religion is changing his life. Moral culture in the process of these changes the role of moral relations is very big. To all this it is achieved through quality education and personnel training implemented in the educational system. Pedagogues currently working in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan along with providing education and training to young people in the spirit of the times, educating them to be loyal to their homeland is one of the priorities. The first priority is to educate the future generation in the spirit of love for the country. Young people who think about the future of our country and people it is also necessary to carry out educational activities aimed at encouraging goodness, honesty, and generosity. About the human mind according to the views established in the East, intelligence is a gift to man. Professional and

intelligence is of two kinds, i.e. natural and professional. Natural intelligence is an innate gift to man is done. Professional intelligence is gained through study, learning and experience. Professional education pedagogues have an honorable and complex task of formation loaded. Therefore, in our country, serious attention is paid to the spiritual and moral education of young people attention is becoming an urgent task today. Development of moral education of youth and morally mature person formation is one of the main tasks before us. Ethical education is an individual's acquisition of social moral experiences and beyond these experiences use in relationships with people, self-regulation includes aspects such as improvement. A morally and educationally mature person also has moral culture. Moral culture is the regulation of social relations of moral life and it is a part created by processing for the purpose of educating people and is the basis of life. The content of moral culture important elements, first of all, moral culture the person as a person, the moral needs of people, a moral goal, a plan that arises from the need to understand needs moral consciousness, human creativity the form of activity is based on moral consciousness and is parallel to it to be implemented - moral creativity, the results of moral creativity include training, manners of walking and standing, moral customs and institutions. Spiritual consists in using the results of moral creativity in life. From their honesty, ethical lifestyle, individual ethical attitudes, moral inclinations and behavior are formed. So, moral culture is above components that make up the specified system that is, it forms the main part. One of our main goals is to inculcate the national idea in the minds of young people. Our country our duty to him, our responsibility for our destiny, neighborhood, work team, family, etc is to educate a sense of responsibility for the lives of loved ones. Family education - it is a place of education and national idea and spirituality in the minds and hearts of young people education begins with the family. Education comes from education, and education comes from education cannot be separated and this process requires high spirituality. Independence also set new demands on the maturity of young people. More than ever the importance of harmonizing inner and outer beauty with morality increases. In young people, only appearance leads to a good aesthetic culture does not come, but his morals are pure, his spiritual world is rich, generous, religious, universal moral values such as high moral culture are required started In the field of spirituality from the first days of independence the need to implement reforms was also envisaged. Pedagogical skill is required in forming the worldview of our youth. It is necessary to remove unnecessary thoughts and ideas from the minds of our youth. The development of our country will be infinitely higher if we give education and training to the youth. every young generation has good thoughts, good words and good deeds. Based on the interests of each young person, it is necessary to direct them to the profession. I. Karimov, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, gave a high level of recognition to our youth and our future generation in his works. The Uzbek people are very hospitable and open-minded people. We must not forget our nationality. Our national values and great history give us spiritual strength. I am glad to see that their interests, thirst for knowledge, and ability to freely express their opinions are at a very high level in the education and upbringing of our young people. The children of an independent country should first of all be given the knowledge of our great history and great thinkers, and the knowledge they have accumulated about their bravery. Pedagogues have a great role in the correct formation of the future

generation's outlook on time. I believe that the coverage of young people in the higher education system is at a very high level. I also think it's good for all of us that schools have switched to 11-year learning processes. A spiritual and educated person can find his place in society. The reason is that they have a good idea, an idea, and of course an offer. I have participated in many competitions in my career. I conducted pedagogical activities in the higher education system. I talked with students and their parents. I ask parents to be attentive to their children. It is necessary to teach our youth to honor the elders and respect the younger ones, not to forget their duties towards their parents and the country. Up to now, young people have been covered in many areas in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this regard, a state policy on youth has been established. Their rights and freedoms are guaranteed. Our young people occupy leading positions in the world in many fields, which is our pride. The flag of our country is flying above. The future of a great country will certainly be great. The fundamental socio-economic and political reforms implemented in our country demand this consistent and continuous changes are being made in the field of education. Upload content raising education to a new level in terms of quality, establishing a system of highly qualified personnel training personnel who can make a decent contribution to occupying a decent place in the labor market sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors is one of our main goals and tasks. There is a need for education further development of work on strengthening the higher spiritual and moral content education, youth respect for national values, humanitarianism and our main goal is to strengthen immunity against high spiritual ideals, foreign ideas and ideologies. Pedagogical, scientific, methodological and practical solutions to these problems, in the necessary conditions for the development of the necessary methodological recommendations is the demand of today. The problem of spiritual and moral formation of a person is raised to this day reached the level of state policy. Future teachers should be prepared for spiritual and moral diversity and it is necessary to develop professional activity in life. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, increasing the scope and quality of education for young people is one of the urgent tasks. Effectiveness of the educational system, improvement of the qualification level of specialists, orientation to teaching involvement of employees in innovative activities, innovative education and introduction of information are among the main tasks. Communication technologies in the educational process in higher educational institutions, development and targeted orientation, modernization of advanced foreign experience is gaining importance in the higher education system. The current stage of social development is characterized by unusualness and priorities aimed at increasing the role of young people in all aspects of life: economy, politics, and spirituality are put forward. The results achieved by young people at the international level are becoming an increasingly visible and influential force. The social activity of the young generation is the most important driving force and is a clear evidence of social development. That is why it is educational in the Republic of Uzbekistan mentally and physically mature generation is a national and nationwide task. This is to consistently and persistently continue the work being done in the path of nobility the goal is the main direction of the current policy of the state. In the conditions of independence, the issues of spiritual values are also becoming relevant. The Uzbek people are mainly distinguished by a system of moral values the leading place should be taken by the sense of family unity and it is necessary to teach to respect the elders, parents,

guests and in general, older and younger people. Uzbek state it is based on traditions, which are the main criteria that determine morality in society.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that moral education and moral culture in our youth essentially, in the socio-economic, political and spiritual development of society appears. The main goal of moral culture is to lead people to the truth and it is a matter of raising him as a perfect person. At the same time moral culture is directly related to social life. Ethical to study the experiences of the peoples of the world in this field of cultural development and application to social life becomes relevant. Moral culture of youth the main measures of formation and moral education are family and work and we believe that it is appropriate to implement it at a high level in the neighborhoods, especially in kindergartens and general secondary schools. One of the main tasks in pedagogy is to form the worldview of young people, to increase their activity in terms of spiritual enlightenment and education. In conclusion, it should be noted that the knowledge and potential of young people in our country is increasing the development and growth of our country is a very important objective law. And now the main goal of every citizen, especially in the field of pedagogy, is to impart knowledge He is serving the prosperity of our selfless compatriots who love this country and this nation the meaning of respecting and promoting the country, its material and spiritual values is very important.

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